

ADMINISTRATIVE LAW AND HUMAN RIGHTS IN THE TIMES OF POPULISM AND DEMOCRATIC DECAY – REFLECTIONS IN THE CONTEXT OF CENTRAL AND EASTERN EUROPE

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ABSTRACT. *Recent years have brought major social changes, including growing dissatisfaction with democratic institutions and the emergence of so-called “illiberal democracy”. Economic crisis and social insecurity also contribute to malfunctioning of democratic societies. Many countries experienced the backsliding from the rule of law and division of power, as well as growing populist and authoritarian tendencies.*

These phenomena have a lot in common with administrative law. Since its main function is to defend the individual against the abuse of power by the state, it is surprising to discover that it is also useful for populist governments and regimes in decaying democracies. By breaking the principles of the rule of law and weakening constitutional values, administrative law alone may not be able to oppose authoritarianism and can even be instrumentally used by such regimes. Therefore, the crucial challenge for administrative law is how to defend democratic values, civil liberties and continue to effectively control and limit the power of the state.

Keywords: *administrative law, human rights, populism, authoritarianism, illiberal democracy, democratic decay.*

The rise of populism in recent years has many causes. One of the most important is that so-called “liberal democracy” often did not propose an attractive offer to the whole society, and focused – at least in the perception of a large proportion of populations – on improving the lives of the elites. A large part of society therefore felt alienated and abandoned by democratic institutions. The citizens have also been losing trust in experts, whereas disinformation and fake news are spreading.

Public administration faces increasing tensions between acting within the principle of the rule of law, and expectations to implement the rule of “*populus*”, or rather the slogans of populist politicians. Those try to exploit the vulnerability or ignorance of the people to gain power and change the functioning of the state by undermining the division of powers and other democratic principles. Populist politicians rarely attempt to address the effectiveness of public administration and making the state more citizen friendly. Responsibility for this often falls on

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the administrative apparatus, as well as the expectation to use their expertise to try to prevent the implementation of dangerous populist ideas.

One of the most important, if not the most important, function of administrative law is the defence of the individual against abuse of power by state authorities. The fundamental constitutional principle, according to which public authorities can act only on the basis and within the limits of the law, is to protect citizens and ensure predictability of the actions of the state by limiting the possibility of interference with the sphere of their rights and freedoms. It can therefore be said that, on the one hand, administrative law answers the populist slogans. On the other hand, administrative law seems to be a particularly useful tool for use by populist governments or “regimes in decaying democracies.” If the authoritarian regime succeeds in overthrowing the limitations of constitutional and human rights axiology, it may turn out that administrative law alone does not have sufficient resources and a separate, independent system of values that could protect individuals from abuse of power [9, p. 195-222].

Western and Eastern paradigm of power

Reflections on the phenomena of populism, decaying democracy and authoritarianism are worth putting in a broader context. An interesting point of reference is the analysis of two different paradigms of power on the East-West axis¹. The extent of the differences of legal and political systems between these two paradigms is particularly evident in Europe, but, of course, countries on other continents can also be analysed according to these criteria. These two concepts of power have also a visible effect on populism and the shape of democracy – “liberal” and so-called “illiberal” – as will be further discussed in this chapter.

These two paradigms of power – Western and Eastern – are characterised by specific, opposing features. First of all, in the West, citizens have the influence on the shape of central and local power, and local power is not dependent on the centre. Even in the countries where society has no influence on who becomes king (and there are still a lot of such countries in Western Europe), special laws are in force, determining precisely how the succession of the throne takes place, how central power functions and what are the relations between its

¹ The concept of paradigms of power was taken from the essay of J. Stępień, *Wschodni i zachodni paradygmat władzy publicznej*, [The Eastern and Western paradigms of public authority], in : A. Gołębiowska, P.B. Zientarski (eds.), *Funkcjonowanie samorządu terytorialnego – uwarunkowania prawne i społeczne*, [The functioning of local government – legal and social conditions], Kancelaria Senatu, Warszawa 2016. However, it is necessary to make an explanation here that the characterisation of these paradigms has a theoretical dimension, that is, the ‘pure’ types are located on the extreme sides of the spectrum, and that this is not a typically geographical dimension. Meanwhile, in practice there are many intermediate types, located on this axis between the two extremes.

various elements. In the West, therefore, there is a division of power, with the assumption that the various parts are to be balanced and controlled.

On the other hand, in the Eastern paradigm of power, citizens have no significant influence on the shape of central power nor on local authorities – everything that happens locally depends on the centre. The elections are held in the Eastern paradigm countries also, however even if they appear to be democratic, they are in fact just a plebiscite of the leader’s popularity. Neither the way of conducting the election campaign, nor the possibility of participation of opposition groups, nor the existence of real political competition, nor the presence of fair rules of the game (including equal access to media and organisation of meetings with citizens), and finally the possibility of impartial verification of the electoral process and outcome – do not function according to the same principles as are established in the countries of the Western paradigm.

An important part of the Western paradigm is also the role of law, or *lex est rex* – where the law is called king, as opposed to monarchy unfettered by the law¹. In the East, the will of the emperor, first secretary or president prevailed over the law. The notion of *lex est rex* was not only the slogan used in the former Polish-Lithuanian Commonwealth, but also – in the form of *Rechtstaat* or *rule of law* – was the basis of the paradigm of public authority in Western Europe. Recalling Hans Kelsen, the founder of the European concept of constitutional courts, it can be added that until there is an independent body capable of effectively abrogating an unconstitutional law, the Constitution is only a collection of pious wishes. But if something is a collection of pious wishes, it certainly cannot be regarded as a normative act.

Another important element of the paradigm of power in the West is properly implemented decentralisation and local self-government. The transfer of state powers to the regional and local level undoubtedly serves to build the subjectivity of local communities, their independence and autonomy. Local self-government also has a chance to be an alternative to populist governments – above all because the so-called “illiberal democracies” and populist governments tend to centralise power and deprive the self-government of competences [11], promising the society better effectiveness of central government’s performance. Meanwhile, it is at the local level that the effects of properly implemented public policies and changes in public administration are seen the best and the fastest².

¹ However, this argument can be somewhat nuanced in the context of absolute monarchies in Western Europe, especially in the era before the ‘enlightened absolutism’.

² Interest arguments to support this claim are given by B. Barber in: *If Mayors Ruled the World: Dysfunctional Nations, Rising Cities*, Yale University Press, 2013.

Table 1. Key elements of the Western and Eastern paradigm of public authority

<i>Western Paradigm</i>	<i>The Eastern Paradigm</i>
Citizens have influence on the shape of the central government and the shape of the local authority	Power is not dependent on citizens neither at central nor at local level
Local authority does not depend on the center	Local authority depends on the center
Division of power, rule of law	Unity of power, rule of the individual
Independent courts and independent judges	Courts and judges dependent on political power
Independent media, NGOs, social control	Media and NGOs controlled by the authorities, limited opportunities for social control

Source: own elaboration based on: J. Stępień, *Wschodni i zachodni paradygmat władzy publicznej*, [The Eastern and Western paradigms of public authority], in: A. Gołębiowska, P.B. Zientarski (eds.), *Funkcjonowanie samorządu terytorialnego – uwarunkowania prawne i społeczne*, [The functioning of local government – legal and social conditions], Kancelaria Senatu, Warszawa 2016.

To the aforementioned, more features can be added, including the transparency and credibility of the public authorities, as well as their openness to citizens and responsiveness to their expectations. These aspects concern the freedom of NGOs performance, irrelevant of their different agendas and views; the control and supervision of the public authorities, exercised by free courts; the media, independent of the authorities' control of their actions. They also concern the real competition of various political groups and providing them with equal opportunities of reaching wide masses of citizens with their political programmes – i.e. fair access to funding of political parties (especially if this funding is carried out with the use of public funds), the possibility of unfettered but also unprivileged holding of rallies and meetings, guaranteeing transparency, reporting on activities, introducing anti-corruption mechanisms, controlling lobbying, counteracting nepotism and other pathological phenomena in the exercise of power. It should also provide a real opportunity to hold public debates on issues of importance to society, during which the discussion takes place on equal basis, and where the merit-based arguments win. Finally, it is about protecting the rights of minorities from the dominance of the majority, respecting human and civil rights, caring for the weaker in the context of the privileged position of the stronger (whether economically or politically).

Meanwhile, in the Eastern paradigm, even if some of these elements are officially present, they are actually apparent and artificial. The separation of powers,

although formally introduced constitutionally, does not actually exist – the legislature and the judiciary are subordinated to the executive branch of power. Free media often do not exist or have limited opportunities for action. Opposition politicians have restricted access to public debate and are often eliminated from political play (in extreme cases even physically). A citizen who clashes with authoritarian power has no chance of winning, because the law is used instrumentally, and the judges might not have the courage to oppose the political power. Also, human rights, even if literally introduced by legislation, do not genuinely impact the situation of the individuals, in particular members of groups that are vulnerable or discriminated against. Thus, the law does not protect the citizen, and the citizen himself has no confidence in the state and its institutions, often treating them as unfavourable, or even hostile. Populist slogans become even more appealing to the common imagination when their priorities focus on security and the possibility of obtaining some short-term benefits.

Populism and “illiberal democracy”

In the context of the shifting of some political systems on the axis of the West-East paradigm, the concept of so-called “illiberal democracy” is becoming increasingly popular. The term was first used in the 1990s by American political scientist Fareed Zakaria [16] in connection with the apparent reverse of the previous dominance of “liberal democracy”. Firstly, in Asia and Latin America, and then more and more often in Europe, there was the need to replace “liberal democracy” with a more efficient model. This demand was met with expectations of the societies disappointed by the limited achievements of previously governing liberal parties.

The criticism of the current model of democracy (referred to as “liberal democracy”) has been mostly focused on the concept of “check and balance” and the principle of the division of power. For the supporters of the so-called “illiberal democracy”, democratic system is primarily a way of electing a government, which is formed basing on the general elections held once every few years. Thus, populist forces present themselves as proponents of “true” or “effective” democracy. Of course, from the point of view of democratic principles (above all, the rule of law and the exercise of power by the majority while respecting the rights of minorities), such understanding of democracy is at least inappropriate and can lead – and often already does – to the construction of an authoritarian system [6, pp. 172-173].

Meanwhile, the difference between democracy and “illiberal democracy” can be reduced to the shortest and most blunt comparison between a chair and an electric chair – the object is similar, but the use is completely different. Democracy, in the most simplified way, means the rule of the majority while respec-

ting the rights of minorities, combined with appropriate mechanisms to control power. The so-called “illiberal democracies” thus retain certain elements of democratic governance, especially free elections, but seek to limit civil liberties and abolish the restrictions of power. “Illiberal democracy” undermines the value of institutional pluralism, in which local authorities – together with the private and non-governmental sectors, the judiciary and independent control bodies – limit the power of the central government and prevent the consolidation of power. The argument concerning the influence of populism on the construction of an authoritarian state and the situation of citizens in the context of their rights thus gains an additional dimension¹.

The classical understanding of democracy is also challenged by the concept of sacrificing at least some rights and freedoms in the name of better economic competitiveness, greater efficiency of the state, strong-handed governments to provide citizens with a sense of security². The abandonment of the achievements of “liberal democracy”, the construction of another type of “democracy” (should it still be considered a democracy?), reforming the state towards a unitary model of power and its transmission, the introduction of political, administrative and information monopolies inevitably lead to authoritarianism. Its most vivid, totalitarian example can be seen not only in North Korea, but also in Russia³ and Belarus.

Populism and administrative law

In recent years, Poland has joined Hungary in the infamous category of countries in democratic decay [8], and similar trends can also be seen in other European countries [2, pp. 9-36]. The use of administrative law to marginalise opposition and political opponents is increasingly popular, as it turns out to be more effective than more sophisticated instruments of criminal or civil law. For authoritarian governments it is easier to use administrative measures, such as controlling the media and marginalising independent media by administrative acts, marginalising social organisations through administrative decisions (restric-

¹ However, research on “illiberal democracy” and a new type of populism are at an early stage of development, with few empirical studies on which it is possible to draw general conclusions. A more in-depth understanding of the so-called illiberal democracy and the practice of populist governments is needed to address the questions on mechanisms that could effectively prevent democracy from falling into populist authoritarianism.

² For example, in Hungary, “illiberal democracy” has become an official state doctrine. Prime Minister Viktor Orbán said in his most famous speech: “*We need to state that a democracy is not necessarily liberal. Just because something is not liberal, it still can be a democracy. Moreover, it could be and needs to be expressed, that probably societies founded upon the principle of the liberal way to organize a state will not be able to sustain their world-competitiveness in the following years and more likely they will suffer a setback, unless they are able to substantially reform themselves*”, at: <https://budapestbeacon.com/full-text-of-viktor-orbans-speech-at-baile-tusnad-tusnadfurdo-of-26-july-2014/>

³ Especially after full-scale armed aggression against Ukraine on February 24, 2022.

tion or withdrawal of funding, refusal to register assemblies and demonstrations), administrative surveillance mechanisms or economic measures (employment and dismissal of officials, withdrawal of permits or licences, privatisation, public procurement) [9, p. 204]. Once again, it turns out that administrative law can be used by populist politicians in a very instrumental way and serve as a carrier of authoritarian tendencies.

In the context of populism and so-called “illiberal democracy”, the role of administrative law seems to be specifically important. Undoubtedly, it evolves with changes in the paradigms of public administration and trends in public management. During the period of dominance of the Weberian concept of legalistic bureaucracy, administrative law served to delimit the spheres of freedom of the state and the freedom of the citizen, protecting the latter from abuse of power by the state administration. Later, in the New Public Management model, administrative law was seen as interfering with the effective functioning of the public administration and was critically assessed based on its functioning. The emphasis was placed on the excessive growth of regulation, which was seen as limiting the possibility of action by the public administration. However, the current increase in populist tendencies and the abuse of instruments of the administrative law, being used to dismantle the so-called “liberal democracy”, point to the need to return to the protective function of this branch of law. This change should be reflected not only in the context of actions of the state administrative apparatus, but also in addressing inequalities or restrictions on access to public services, which are inevitable in the conditions of marketisation of the process of performing public tasks [12].

Administrative law therefore has a very important role to play. As a guarantor of civil rights and liberties, it should prevent the abuse of power and the danger of democracy falling to tyranny. However, it might not be axiologically strong enough to prevent the democratic decay. That is because administrative law is secondary and dependent on the values represented by constitutional law, and deprived of specific and autonomous norms, values and principles. Therefore, it seems to be easier for the authoritarian regimes to take over administrative law instruments, especially after the dismantling the system of civil rights protection. For this reason, it should be ensured and significantly strengthened, as well as used as the component of human rights and social rights, as without them the demands of populist politicians shall naturally reach ever more fertile ground. It is in the interest of the citizens to enforce electoral promises and to demand the effectiveness of state action, but not at the cost of centralising powers and slipping into “illiberal democracy” and authoritarianism. Democratic values must therefore be guarded not only by an effective law and the ability to enforce it, but above all by an independent justice system with independent judges, as well as effective control mechanisms against the actions of the authorities.

The concept of dual state

The process of misusing the administrative law in “illiberal” or “decaying” democracies is illustrated by the concept of “dual state” consisting of two components: ‘normative state’ and ‘prerogative state’. Those two components coexist, are used in parallel, and the nature of application of the law depends on the subject of this application, so on whom the law is exercised. The normative state, as in the classic doctrine of administrative law in the system of rule of law, aims to protect the citizens from the abuse of power, i.a. by ensuring proper standards of law-making and judicial review. However, the actions of the prerogative state are directed to implementation of the political and ideological agenda of the ruling party, and are aimed at consolidating power, marginalising the opposition, and strengthening authoritarian tendencies.

Graphic 1. Components of ‘dual state’

Source: own graphic based on B. Schotel, *Administrative law as a dual state. Authoritarian elements of administrative law*, Hague Journal on the Rule of Law, 2021, No 13.

Administrative law seems to have the characteristics that facilitate its functioning in a “dual state” and can therefore be used by populist and authoritarian regimes. These features include: universal and comprehensive judicial review of administrative acts, presumption of legality of administrative acts, enforcement privilege for the administration, respect by courts of the separation of policies, and the establishment of facts by the administration [9, p. 207]. Attempts can be made to influence these attributes primarily by exerting political pressure on the judiciary and judges, as well as limiting their independence by affecting the organisation of administrative courts and the appointment of judges. Therefore, if a populist power succeeds in breaking the principles of the rule of law and weakening constitutional values, the same administrative law on its own will not be able to oppose authoritarianism and can even be instrumentally used by such a regime [9, p. 203].

While populism deals with mass politics and the consequences of elections, analyses of this phenomenon focus on the attractiveness of populist politics for voters [5, pp. 1-24], the potential impact of voting on populists and their impact

on governments. However, almost all discussion on governance so far is limited to situations related to elections, political parties, social movements, and in some cases also the impact on legislative and judicial powers. Little information can be found on the impact of populism on public administration, administrative law and even on the state in general¹.

This deficiency of analysis of the links between populism and administrative law does not contribute to explanation why there are possibility of regimes' instrumental use of administrative law in "decaying democracies", and indeed – as Bas Schotel claims – the specific nature of administrative law, which makes it useful for authoritarian systems. The characteristics of administrative law, unlike, for example, criminal or civil law, may predestine this law to be used as an instrument of a prerogative state [9]. The law still shall protect the citizens – but only those who are obedient to political power. It will not have the same function when applied to the opponents of the regime in a prerogative state, as it will be often used against them [9, p. 202]. Such a dual, even schizophrenic character of the state contributes to the decomposition of peace and harmony in social life.

This theoretical approach used to examine the role of administrative law in the countries in democratic decay show the dangerous potential that needs to be carefully studied. More efforts need to be made to prevent it from being used as the instrument of oppression by the authoritarian regime. While part of the population can still enjoy the ordering and protective nature of administrative law, at the same time the other can be persecuted by politically charged application of administrative decisions. It seems to be a convenient tool for authoritarian regime, as perceived as less harsh than criminal law measures (and certainly less spectacularly catch the media attention), while reaching the same target, that is aiming to control and subordinate the citizens.

Summary

The above considerations show that treating populism as one of the most important phenomena in modern politics and administration has its justification. Populist movements bring new challenges and significant distortions to established political practices and force to rethink the way the state is governed. Popu-

¹ See: B. Guy Peters, J. Pierre, *Populism and Public Administration: Confronting the administrative state*, "Administration and Society" 2019, Vol. 51(10). The degree of discrepancy between literature analysing populism and research on public policy and administration is illustrated, among others, by the *Oxford Handbook of Populism* (R. Kaltwasser, P. Taggart, P. Ochoa Espejo, P. Ostiguy, op. cit.), This extensive publication (more than 700 pages) does not contain a chapter dedicated to populism and public administration, and terms such as "administration", "bureaucracy", "public governance" and "politics" do not appear in the index. The closest theme in this publication is the chapter on constitutionalism, in which the author made several observations on the impact of populism – including the reflections that populists tend to "occupy" the state and that they engage in mass clientelism, which undoubtedly translates into administrative law and the functioning of public administration. (J.-W. Müller, *Populism and constitutionalism*, in: R. Kaltwasser, C., P. Taggart, P. Ochoa Espejo, P. Ostiguy, op. cit., pp. 590-606).

list politicians seem to have succeeded in disrupting the old order and introducing a new, so-called “illiberal democracy”, but replacing it with effective governance seems much less effective. The global political and economic instability, the crisis linked first to the COVID-19 pandemic and the climate change and then the war in Ukraine, as well as the energy, economic and food crises – these are the real problems and challenges facing not only politicians but also those who act and apply administrative law. As shown above, badly intentioned, or misappropriated norms of administrative law can contribute to strengthening authoritarian tendencies and to deepening the crisis of democracy in many countries, including those established in the Western paradigm of power.

Meanwhile, populists themselves seem to care less about solving the problems of the modern world, and more about guaranteeing themselves power through winning subsequent elections and paralysing the functioning of the rule of law and balance of power. Populist politicians often do not focus on improving the functioning of public administration and make the state more citizen-friendly but use them in a less sophisticated way in the search for the effective instruments to keep and exercise power, as well as ensure their dominance and irremovability.

Administrative law therefore has a very important role to play in protecting civil rights and liberties, in particular against the authoritarian attempts to abuse power, so frequent in the case of populist governments. The more buffers and brakes are removed, the greater the possibility of democracy moving towards so-called “illiberal democracy” and authoritarianism. The important responses to these challenges also include transparency and credibility of the public institutions, inclusivity, and openness to citizens, as well as responsiveness to their expectations. These values are implemented by the freedom of action of non-governmental organisations with different programmes and worldviews; by the control and supervision of public authorities, exercised by free courts, media, independent controlling and auditing bodies.

When looking for an antidote to populism, it is therefore necessary to focus on constitutional values and instruments, as well as pairing them effectively with well-established and correctly applied administrative law. It is also important to educate citizens about the functioning of a democratic state and rule of law, as they are the guarantees of their rights and freedoms and can protect from the temptations of populists’ authoritarian actions.

Bibliographical references:

1. Barber B. (2013), *If Mayors Ruled the World: Dysfunctional Nations, Rising Cities*, Yale University Press
2. Daly T. (2019). *Democratic Decay: Conceptualizing an Emerging Research Field*, “Hague Journal on the Rule of Law” (2019), 11:9-36.

3. Gottheil M. (2017), *Administrative Law and the Rise of Populism*, April 27, 2017
4. Guy Peters B., J. Pierre (2019), *Populism and Public Administration: Confronting the Administrative, State Administration and Society* Vol 51, Issue 10, 2019
5. Kaltwasser, C. R., Taggart, P., Espejo, P. O., Ostiguy, P. (2017). *Oxford handbook of populism*. Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press.
6. Kołtuniak Ł. (2017), *Nieliberalna demokracja a państwo prawa. Przypadek Węgier Wiktora Orbana*, „Internetowy Przegląd Prawniczy” TBSP UJ 2017/8
7. Müller, J.-W. (2017). *Populism and constitutionalism*. In Kaltwasser, C. R., Taggart, P., Espejo, P. O., Ostiguy, P. (Eds.), *Oxford handbook of populism* (pp. 590-606). Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press
8. Sadurski W. (2019) „Poland’s Constitutional Breakdown” (OUP, 2019).
9. Schotel B. (2021). *Administrative Law as a Dual State. Authoritarian Elements of Administrative Law*, “Hague Journal on the Rule of Law” (2021) 13:195-222
10. Stępień J., (2016) *Wschodni i zachodni paradygmat władzy publicznej*, in: „Funkcjonowanie samorządu terytorialnego – uwarunkowania prawne i społeczne”, Redakcja naukowa A. Gołębiowska i P.B. Zientarski, Warszawa
11. Sześciło D. (2019) *Is There A Room For Local And Regional Self-Government In The Illiberal Democracy? Struggle Over Recentralization Attempts In Poland*, *Studia Iuridica LXXIX*
12. Sześciło D. (2019), *Od Juristenmonopol do marginalizacji. O zanikającym paradygmacie prawniczym w administracji publicznej*, *Państwo I Prawo* 4/2019
13. Taggart, P. (2000). *Populism*. Buckingham, UK: Open University Press
14. Weber M. (1978), *Economy and Society*, Berkeley: University of California Press
15. Yesilkagit, K. (2018). *Bureaucracy under authoritarian rule: Autonomy and resilience of administrative institutions under conditions of democratic backsliding*. Leiden University, The Netherlands
16. Zakaria F. (1997), *The rise of illiberal democracy*, “Foreign Affairs” 1997, issue 22.

Web resources:

1. Drezner, D. (2018, July 18). *The infectious incompetence of the populists*. The Washington Post: <https://www.washingtonpost.com/pb/news/posteverything/wp/2018/07/16/the-infectious-incompetence-of-the-populists/?commentID=&outputType=comment>

2. Fukuyama F. (2018), The Populist Surge, <https://www.the-american-interest.com/2018/the-populist-surge>
3. Mudde C. (2018), Populism in the Twenty-First Century: An Illiberal Democratic Response to Undemocratic Liberalism, 2018, www.sas.upenn.edu/andrea-mitchell-center/cas-mudde-populism-twenty-first-century
4. <https://budapestbeacon.com/full-text-of-viktor-orbans-speech-at-baile-tusnad-tusnadfurdo-of-26-july-2014/>